

Modified IOT-RTP Routing Protocol For Transmission Of Multi-Modal Biomedical Data

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Abstract: With multimodal biomedical signals constituting complex multimedia messages to be transmitted from WBAN over WSN with IoT in e-health monitoring applications there is need for novel routing protocols. Transmission of medical signals and images over Internet of Multimedia Things (IoMT) predominantly face the challenges in ensuring quality sensory data. In this paper energy-efficient routing mechanism based on modified IoT versions of Real time Transport Protocol (RTP) and Real Time Control Protocol (RTCP). The proposed protocol achieves improvement in energy efficiency of 3.02%, reduction in end-end delay of 4ms and Packet loss of 19% respectively.

Keywords: WCE images, RTP, RTCP, Multimedia, IoT, WSN and WBAN.

1. INTRODUCTION

Raising health disorders **requires** interpretation of multimodal medical data for **precision diagnosis** of disease making and accurate identification of disease or disorders. So biomedical signals and images needs to be transmitted to remote locations where further processing and analysis is performed by the medical experts. This **demands** communication of multimedia data over IoT infrastructure and overcome different challenges like delay and loss. **Different data kinds (text, sound, graphics, picture, animations, video, etc.) are included in multimedia signals, which might be time-dependent (sound, video, and animation) or spatially-dependent (text, sound, graphics, picture, animations, video, and so on) (images, text and graphics).** Internet of Multimedia Things (IoMT) is a routing paradigm in which various multimedia objects can interact and coordinate over the Internet [24]. For accurate diagnostic decision different biomedical signals are applied. Significance of each of these signals are discussed in brief in following sections.

Electrocardiogram (ECG) signal is an electrical signal representing functionality of Heart and is used for analysis in identifying cardiac disorders. Cardiovascular Diseases (CVD) is the

leading killer as per World Health Organization (WHO)[32]. The cardiac functionality is reflected in the ECG wave pattern and different types of associated abnormalities in rhythm are termed as Arrhythmias [25]. The graph of normal electrocardiogram waveform is shown in Figure 1.

Electroencephalographic (EEG) waves serve to the examination of a brain activity. EEG signals are the powerful tool that has the capability to reflect all the activities of the brain from all the various parts of the brain viz., Central Nervous System (CNS) which comprised of Spinal cord and Peripheral Nervous System (PNS). Depending on a human brain activity, several types of electroencephalographic (EEG) waves can be distinguished. Deviations of the normal EEG waves corresponding to alpha or beta activity, i.e. sharp spikes, can refer to pathologic patterns accompanying neurological illnesses. Based on a detection of pathologic patterns recurring with period of one or a few seconds in EEG signal, it has been used to diagnose diseases such as epilepsy or polio. Because of the important role of the EEG examination in neurological disease diagnostics it has been considered in this study.

It has been also been that seizures are frequently linked to changes in the circulatory and respiratory systems, such as tachycardia. [16, 18].

Figure 1: ECG sample waveform [6]

Simultaneous ECG recording and EEG testing is a clinical requirement for detecting and determining the clinical significance of co-existing ECG and EEG abnormalities [23]. In the literature it is mentioned that to improve the accuracy of disease detection it is preferable to use more than one modality. Hence with the combination of EEG & ECG signals it is possible to identify cardiac disorders. Therefore in this study ECG and EEG signals have been taken for transmission over IOT.

Wireless Capsule Endoscopy: Capsule endoscopy is used to record inward photos of the gastrointestinal tract to take biopsies and release remedy at unequivocal territories of the entire gastrointestinal tract. The main interest has been identified to be obscure gastrointestinal bleeding diagnosis. High data transfer speeds are required for wireless capsule endoscopes and biomedical image processing (nearly 10 Mbps).

It was discovered that there is association between acute upper gastrointestinal bleeding and ECG changes particularly Right Bundle Branch (RBBB) for around 30% cases. [FA Gamboa]. This clearly illustrates that ECG and WCE image data are related to each other and could be used for identification of cardiac disorders.

Audio signal

In the diagnosis of cardiovascular illness Heart Sound and ECG are two highly essential and widely utilised diagnostic aids.. Morphological similarity between ECG and Heart sounds is useful in detection of a Heart disease. One dimension audio signal extracted from, an open dataset HSCT-11 containing data can be used for performance evaluation of heart sounds biometric systems.

Thus multimodal data contains three 1-D signals and a WCE Image which are related to each other and contribute towards increase in the accuracy of Heart disease detection.

Remote health monitoring

Remote patient monitoring is a technology-based process that allows patients and healthcare providers to monitor their health outside of hospitals. Remote health monitoring has the potential to significantly improve the quality of life for long-term sufferers. It can assist patients with a variety of ailments, although the technology is most commonly used to monitor heart and diabetes conditions [31].

The remainder of the article is covered in following sections. Section 1 introduces biomedical signals and images. Critical review of the existing IOT routing protocols in literature is carried out in section 2. Section 3 presents block diagram of the proposed solution and section 4 contains detailed description of proposed method. Results analysis is performed in section 5 and related conclusions are drawn in the division 6.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section survey of recent IoMT routing protocols are analysed along with their limitations.

Overview of IoT, use-cases and opportunities for horizontal integration between IOT services were explored along with summary of the most important IEEE, IETF and EPC global routing protocols in [3]. The illustration of layered architecture of building blocks and technologies of IoT show the provision for IPv4 and IPv6 based routing of data. Classification of solutions in IOT for smart –cities was addressed and pointed out that energy-consumption and life time of IoT devices are key issues in delivery of solutions [6].

The core idea of the Sea Computing model was realized in CASCR (Context-Awareness in Sea Computing Routing Protocol) for Internet of Things [4]. CASCR has more energy efficiency, prolonged lifetime, and higher Throughput than the protocols like LEACH and SPT [4]. The limitation of CASCR protocol is that number of control packets required is more than others. Further clustering can be applied in IoT networks.

Delgalvis I. et al. proposed a technique for real-time transmission which demonstrated that the buffer size is determined based on multimedia packet dimension and traffic in network and contributes for the introduction of more delay and packet losses. The limitation of this approach is that requirements are stringent for transmission of the multimedia streams [7]. A real-time data model based on a web service was exhibited, and the model components were examined. The demerit of this method was its low energy efficiency [8].

IOMT network routing approach using UDP for real-time exchange over the IoT environment was proposed in [9]. The major drawback lies in its inappropriate representation of the IoT environment where performance parameters like delay jitter was not included in the study. Proposed adaptive version of UDP did not include application layer functions in the multimedia communication [9, 10]. Also no information about end-to-end delay and packet loss was given.

Jingwu C. et al. proposed a energy constraint multimedia scheduling transmission mechanism over an IoT network [11, 12]. The significant limitation is that heterogeneity was not considered in the IoT environment and thus quantification of energy consumption was not available.

Another approach for transmitting video streams over the Internet termed Using an MDC coder, the Adaptive Multiple Description Coding Protocol (AMDCP) was created [13]. Multi-flow At the session layer, the Real-time Transport Protocol (MRTP), which is developed for ad hoc networks, combines MDC and transport protocol techniques to partition multimedia streams into flows that are conveyed along a dedicated path. [14]. But it was for ad hoc networks only and is not for IoT systems because of scalability, diversity issues and No multimedia transmission over IOT was considered. Thus exact values for each performance metric have not been reported in many studies which focussed on individual metrics only.

The Adaptive Multi-flow Real-time Multimedia Transport Protocol (Adam RTP) for proposed for WSN to modify RTP and RTCP [15]. Adam RTP mitigates congestion and ensures good QoS, lesser energy consumption for multimedia transmission.

More significantly it can be noted that most of the studies concentrated on only 1 type of data and particularly multimodal data with 2-D and 1-D signals have not been reported in the literature. Hence the Objective of the work is to develop energy efficient low loss, and low-delay routing protocols for communication of Multimedia data over IOT networks.

3. Experimental setup and materials

Simulation based experiments are conducted using four sensory data taken from different datasets. ECG data is taken from MIT-BIH Arrhythmia dataset [26], Heart sound Audio signal [21], EEG [27] and Image from [29]. All the four data are fed to the routing module at a time where the priority is assigned for each data and the further transferred over the IOT network.

Thing speak software: It is an IoT assessment platform that facilitates aggregation, picturization and examines live data streams in the cloud. Performance of the modified IoT-RTP and RTCP protocols is carried out using MATLAB and later assessed using Thing Speak.

4. Proposed Solution

Fig: Multimedia Based Remote patient monitoring over IOT network Hospital

Figure 2: Block diagram of IoT –RTP based E-health Monitoring Network

For Cardiac disease detection four different signals EEG, ECG, audio sound (Heart sound) and WCE are acquired and transmitted to medical server via IoT infrastructure using IoT-RTP protocol as shown in Figure 2.

The challenge lies in routing data by assigning while simultaneously extending life time of the underlying entire WSN. For this purpose modified IoT versions of RTP and RTCP protocols are deployed. The work flow of modified IoT-RTP protocol is shown in Figure 3.

Flow Diagram

Fig 4.3: shows Flow diagram

FORMATION OF THE CLUSTERS IN WSN

The process of cluster formation, determination of cluster head and base station of each signal is discussed as follows. Let the clusters be represented as CL_1, CL_2, CL_3 and their base stations are b_1, b_2, b_3 respectively. Equation (1) states that k-means objective function with base station b_i , which can be applied to update the CL_i using equation (2).

$$F(b_i, CL_i) = \sum_{i=1}^b \sum_{q_i \in CL_i} ||q_i - b_i||^2 \text{-----(1)}$$

$$b_i = \frac{1}{CL_i} \sum_{q_i \in CL_i} q_i \text{-----(2)}$$

For determination of distance between sensors and base stations Euclidean distance is used and is given by equation below.

$$D(q_i, q_j)^2 = ||q_i - q_j||^2 = \sum_{i=1, j=i+1}^d (q_i, q_j)^2 = (q_i - q_j) \cdot (q_i - q_j) \text{-----(3)}$$

In this work, all datasets are converted into packets, these packets has session ID, sub-SID, sub-sub-SID, flow ID, sub-sub-FID, node counter and timing setup for counter of packets shown in Fig.4.

IOT-RTP Protocol

The measure of media session in the IoT frameworks may likewise be all of a sudden expanded or diminished because of quick joining or leaving of members. In this manner, the versatile condition of RTP ought to suit numerous adjustments in the conventional RTP variant so as to work regardless of the IoT condition challenges. The IoT-RTP manages the IoT interactive media session as little parts. Thus, the mixed media session ought to be partitioned into straightforward sessions. Each sub flow ought to be distinguished by whole number pursued by its unique stream identifier.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
V	PT					Session ID			Sub-SID			Sub-Sub-SID			Flow ID		Sub-FID		Sub-Sub-FID			
Counter for sensor node																			Thing type			
Level of Normal Energy for each node													Critical level measurement of energy									
Extended Sequence number																Thing state			Priority			
Time stamp																						

Figure 4: IoT –RTP Header format [1]

E: Number of transmitter nodes

G: Total number of sub-sessions

Y: Subsequent session ids

R: Capacity of Network for all the sessions

R_{div} : The network's capacity after the division at sub sessions levels

W: Count of the sub-flows

IoT-RTP Algorithm:

1. if $\sum_{j=1}^E \text{session Id} \leq R$
 Normal state
 else
2. for X=1 to G
3. begin

if $\sum_{j=1}^{E/G} \text{session Id} \leq R_{\text{div}}$)

Normal state

4. else $pf_i = \frac{\text{session id}}{w}$

Normal state

else

5. for $i=1$ to 4

pf_i , RTP should be used for transmission and cloud storage.

6. End

IoT-RTCP Protocol

In the same way, the flexible form of RTCP analyses the condition of the IOT structure when it comes to the transmission of blended media streams. Furthermore, never-before-seen blended media coding should be considered for reducing RTCP reports while maintaining data transmission across IOT structures.

Prioritization of control reports should be related with this goal to achieve it. In IOT-RTCP, Sender reports (SR) and receiver reports (RR) should be refreshed by adding various fields to gather unequivocal information about the IOT structure.

IoT-RTP algorithm

BT: Time set aside for receiving packets, In the interval before the report is received (RR).

GL: Top level of entire multimedia session.

OL: Mid level of divided session.

NL: Bottom level of divided session.

DEE: End-end-delay.

SL: Packet loss.

U: Jitter with delay

RR: Report on the reception of the packet.

1. if($TP < BT$)

2. begin

3. for $P=1$ to GL

4. begin

5. for $N=1$ to ML

6. begin

7. for $Q=1$ to NL

8. begin

9. if (DEE, SL, U are normal values)

10. begin

11. IoT-RTCP stopped the additional fields

12. Report on the reception of the packet

13. $RR_P = RR_N + RR_Q$

14. end

15. else

16. increase BT
17. include additional fields of IOT-RTCP
18. $RR_P = RR_N + RR_Q$
19. end
20. $RR_{ML} = RR_{GL} + RR_N$
21. end
22. $RR_{GL} = RR_N + RR_{ML}$
23. end

5. RESULT ANALYSIS

This section presents results obtained from the simulation of the modified IoT-RTP protocol using MATLAB tool.

Figure 5. Multimedia data Transmission through IoT network

In this paper, performance evaluation of the IoT-RTP and IoT-TCP protocols has been carried out using 4 sensory data. The multi-modal data namely ECG, EEG, Audio signal and WCE image are transmitted via IoT network to the medical server. These data are prioritized and then transmitted over the WSN networks running RTP and RTCP protocol. The behavioural analysis of IoT-RTP and IoT-RTCP protocols has been studied when data with different dimensions are transmitted. The impact on network metrics indicate superior performance of the IoT versions of RTP protocols. All the data are written into IoT channel via Thingspeak and read at reception end. Figure 6 illustrates transmission and reception of Multimedia data over IoT network.

Figure 6. Statistics of RTP-RTCP protocol by using thingSpeak.com

Table 1: Comparative statement between previous work and proposed work

Parameter	Previous work [1]	Proposed work
Packet loss	37.42%	19%
End to End delay	200ms	196ms
Energy Efficiency	18.35%	21.33%

The performance comparison of the proposed modified IoT-RTP over IoMT network is shown in Table1. From the obtained results, it is concluded that there is reduction of packet loss by18.42%, energy efficiency increased by 3.02% and end to end delay is reduced by 4ms.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper modified IoT versions of RTP and RTCP protocols were subjected to transmission of multimedia data comprising of three 1-D signals and one image. The multimodal data was chosen to increase the detection accuracy of the Heart diseases. The network performance improvement in energy efficiency by 3.02%, reduction in end-end delay by 4ms and Packet loss of 19% respectively is achieved has been attained because of the prioritization criterion introduced in IoT-RTP protocols. Further improvements of other network performance metrics can be done by pursuing compression techniques along with novel data driven routing mechanisms

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